

Energy is an external barrier to efficiency gains to constructions pourable requirements

G. Uderbaeva,

A. Jadigerov

Abstract: *This is it in the article improve energy efficiency from the point of view of the external barrier to constructions pourable requirements today state level current from issues one is considered especially this problems solution in reaching village their houses to heating to go energy to determine and reduction is separate importance occupation it is said that*

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Reducing energy consumption in buildings and comfort micro- which is poured into buildings and structures from the point of view of climate creation one how much requirements is available. Current in the day energy spending reduce according to Consistent measures are being implemented and accepted by the state the decision being made and also in the statutes own on the contrary is finding

Uzbekistan Republic President "2019 – 2030 years during Uzbekistan Republic of "green" to the economy transition "On approval of the strategy" of 2019 year 4 PQ in October – 4477 – number in decisions: energy audit and energetic of passporting duties building and structures

energy of consumption real indicators identify them valid normative (normative) to documents according to defined indicators with compare, to standards suitable didn't come indicators analysis to do and in the rooms microclimate adjustable parameters valid to standards compatibility provided without energy efficiency increase events work exit, also ecological to standards compatibility analysis to do set poured.

Energoaudit in transfer energy audit according to defined in order approved normative to documents according to in the building fuel – energy resources consumption in doing effect showing the following factors evaluation in the eye held: of the building external barriers (walls, windows, the roof and floor); heating system, ventilation system, hot water supply system, energy consumption doer all equipment, cooling system (air conditioning), of YoER alternative sources organize done[2]. This is it to the decision according to buildings in construction and reconstruction to do energy efficiency in the process The most effective measures to increase are external obstacle insulation of structures is to do.

Almost half of energy consumption in developed countries is residential. space is used for heating buildings. So save resources one of the main methods is to increase the energy efficiency of buildings consists of That's it because of right now Europe in the states housing to build design in the process building energy economy and to him to gomaterials preliminary analysis by doing will be considered.

In houses heat of energy to disappear in determining each one from the construction to go energy to determine necessary. External obstacle from constructions the window and doors around temperature area is variable. Such

change external the wall thickness and the window windowsbetween to size depends being the window on the edges temperature sharp variable will be Window edges on the surface of temperature decline, from the windowexcess heat of the amount spend to be take come and external the wallit is necessary to increase the thickness. However, the heat balance of buildings at the expense of from the window excess spend happening heat quantity the majority cases account not available. This while room inside the air temperature to decrease take will come Window and the window from the edges spend happening excessthe calculation of the amount of heat is complicated and the calculation takes a lot of time. To determine the amount of excess heat consumed from the window, the wall The temperature field around the window boundaries with prof. K.F. Fokin by calculated.

The amount of excess heat consumed from the edges of the window is as followsformula determined using:

$$Q_k = \alpha_0 \cdot (t_i - t_k) \cdot v$$

this on the ground Q_k - one meter to the length have the window from the edge passing heat quantity, W/m.°C; t_i - in the room the air temperature, °C; t_k - the window slope

the edge average temperature, °C; c – the window of the slope width, m.

The closer the window is to the inner surface of the wall, the more inclined the window is from the edges spend happening heat quantity that's all less will be however to the window nearby wall of the inner surface the temperature is sharp decreases.

The window to the wall installation condition, of the wall temperature

for the sake of it effectreach of the window heat transfer and to the coefficient depends not.

Current in the day in our country wide being used modern from the profile manufactured double-glazed windows compared to old single-glazed wooden windows significant (plastic rums by 20%) is energy efficient.

QMQ 2.03.10 – 95* "Energy efficient buildings the roofs design" according to the roof and the beds design requirements and rules, attic coatings, without an attic the roof closures, of doomsday efficient heat protectionstandards for the selection of materials and constructive solutions are presented.It was necessary to design the barrier structures of the roofs addition recommendations given. In the manual is available buildings the roofsheat protection qualities, operational reliability and durabilityeternity increase in order to reconstruction to do issues considered.

Roofs of individual residential buildings in rural areas heat insulation layer of attic partitions, local materials, in particular, from plates made of cane installation and by design recommendations are given .

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